

Tonolli Memorial Award

The Tonolli Fund of SIL was created in 1985 through a bequest from Vittorio and Livia Tonolli, well known limnologists at the Istituto Italiano di Idrobiologia in Pallanza, Italy. The purpose of the fund is to provide assistance to young limnologists in developing countries and encourage them to join SIL. Information about the fund can be found at [LIMNOLOGY.ORG/tonolli-memorial-award](https://www.limnology.org/tonolli-memorial-award). Below are two reports from recent Tonolli Fund recipients.

Argentina

Shallow lakes from the Salado River basin (Buenos Aires, Argentina): effects of anthropogenic activities

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Shallow lakes are the predominant aquatic ecosystems in the Pampa Region, playing an important role in local economies by providing ecosystem services such as irrigation, recreation and fishing. These water bodies are naturally enriched in nutrients (Quirós and Drago, 1999), although in the last years some have begun to change from a eutrophic to hypertrophic state due to nitrogen and phosphorus discharges related to human activities (Portela *et al.*, 2009). Besides, these lakes are located in a lowland river basin, so they are affected by runoff from agriculture and other pollutants (Vera *et al.*, 2010), causing an overall deterioration in water quality and ecosystem services.

The Salado River basin is located in the centre of the Pampa Region, one of the most productive areas of Argentina. The aquatic environments associated with this basin are strongly affected by a high heterogeneity in land use. In particular, the upper basin is characterized by agricultural use (soybean-corn-wheat rotations) with high requirements of agrochemicals; while the lower basin is characterized by livestock and pastures (Gabellone *et al.*, 2005). These differences between basins affect the phytoplankton (Sánchez *et al.*, 2021) and bacterioplankton (Nuozzi *et al.*, in prep.) community compositions. Here, our main objective was to characterize land use in the areas surrounding shallow lakes throughout the Salado River basin, in order to disentangle its effect on water quality and sanitary state of these water bodies.

In October 2019 we sampled 15 shallow lakes (24 sampling points) from the headwaters to the mouth of the Salado River. All water bodies were

Fig. 1: Map depicting the 14 shallow lakes and the wetland selected for the study. The Salado River is highlighted in red, the upper basin lakes in green and the lower basin lakes in orange. Lake name abbreviations are written in parentheses.

connected to the river and presented different levels of anthropogenic impact. We also included a wetland with less anthropogenic impact located near Campos del Tuyú National Park (Ramsar site), as a control (Fig. 1). Environmental and biological variables were assessed for each sampling point (Secchi disk transparency, temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, conductivity, turbidity, organic and inorganic suspended solids, soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP), ammonium, dissolved organic carbon, chlorophyll-a). We also quantified atrazine concentrations and fecal indicator bacteria (*Escherichia coli*) to evaluate the water quality and sanitary state of these aquatic ecosystems. Land use in the 1 km zone around each shallow lake was categorized as agriculture, livestock, urbanization and wetlands using public geospatial information (de Abelleyra *et al.*, 2019).

Statistical analysis of the data separated lakes into the upper and lower basins. The main distinguishing factors were atrazine, agriculture and SRP for the upper basin and livestock for the lower basin including the wetland (Fig. 2). Agricultural land use was positively correlated with atrazine and SRP and negatively correlated with dissolved oxygen. The same variables showed opposite correlations with livestock. The wetland showed no agriculture use and undetectable atrazine concentrations; however it was affected by livestock activities.

Indicator bacteria, such as *E. coli* surprisingly did not correlate with any variables. However, in some lakes, the *E. coli* levels were above the limits established for recreational waters (US EPA, 1986). Concentrations of the herbicide atrazine exceeded the reference levels associated with chronic toxicity for phytoplankton communities (Pratt *et al.*, 1988) only in one lake.

In conclusion, anthropogenic activities in this basin affect not only water quality and the sanitary state of the shallow lakes, but also the ecosystem services they provide. Even so, we are unaware to what extent this affects the upper levels of the food-web of these lakes. Our results support the hypothesis that the upper basin is under more anthropogenic pressure due to higher concentrations of SRP and atrazine as a consequence of land use tied to agriculture. The fact that *E. coli* was not correlated with any other variable suggests that the presence of this fecal indicator bacteria is related to point discharges of untreated sewage. Altogether, this creates a situation of great concern for both ecosystems and human health, as these shallow lakes are used for recreational purposes and provide many other ecosystem services. In further studies we will test the effect of land use on bacterioplankton communities throughout the entire Salado River Basin shallow lakes.

Fig. 2: a) Bubble scatter charts of changes in atrazine concentrations relative to longitude and b) SRP concentrations relative to longitude; c) pie chart land use (agriculture, livestock, urbanization and wetlands) for upper and lower Salado River basins

Our study will help policy makers to formulate knowledge-based decisions and to recommend more effective models of protection, management and restoration of these valuable aquatic environments.

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